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TOWARDS EUROPEAN AND UKRAINIAN SUSTAINABLE UNIVERSITIES PARTNERSHIPS

BEST PRACTICES OF EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES ALLIANCES IN SOLIDARITY WITH UKRAINE

2025 EDITION

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FOREWORD

Unfortunately, the war in Ukraine has been ongoing for over three years, with innocent people continuing to die. Although world politics has changed dramatically, the human values that guide us in life remain unchanged. In the academic community, it is important to recall ideas that bring people, nations, countries, languages and cultures together, because universities are places of diversity by their very nature. Young people, who will one day become leaders of social groups, gain their education and develop their characters at universities. This is why it is so crucial for the spirit of democracy to always be present within the walls of the university. It is also vital that universities support one another, especially in times of war when many challenges arise. Each university is located in a particular country and connected to a specific region, yet the challenges faced by universities and their graduates are often transregional and transnational. For this reason, and in this spirit, the University of Strasbourg and Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań have supported Ukrainian universities since Russia's aggression began. It warms our hearts to see that so many in Europe share our point of view. Ukrainian universities are educating a generation today that will establish democratic societal structures and rebuild an independent state in the future. We hope for lasting peace. One of the most visible signs is the cooperation between European universities alliances and Ukrainian universities. Much has already been achieved, but there is scope for even more.

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INTRODUCTION

Russian full-scale invasion of Ukraine has changed the European Union. Has it changed higher education in Europe in solidarity with Ukraine, and how can our Alliances be instrumental?

Purpose of this report is to highlight what we as higher education institutions (HEIs) have done in solidarity with Ukraine since the full-scale invasion of this country, and what more could be done if additional political and financial support is provided. Across the European Union (EU), our Alliances' bottom-up initiatives have become one aspect of the HEIs' connections with Ukraine to provide assistance, help (re)build academic capacities and develop long-term relationships in the perspective of the reconstruction and modernisation of this country. Despite the absence of dedicated funds, a shared understanding of what has to be done and what Alliances could offer has emerged, with a variety of solutions that are presented here.

The cross-border grassroots actions of Alliances are often not so visible, although they are numerous, fast-evolving and today acknowledged as an important contribution to the efforts made by HEIs in Ukraine in order to maintain their everyday and long-term activities. Events such as at the European parliament in Strasbourg in March 2024, followed by a first record of best practices that constituted the first edition of this report, and the EAIE workshop in Toulouse in September 2024 disseminated good practices. Since April 2025, FOREU4ALL Community of Practice has launched a topical group on "Cooperation with Ukraine" and it will hold an in-person workshop in Prague in October 2025 to present some Alliances' cases and identify possible cooperation models and processes, with the support and in presence of the Czech Ministry of Education and the Czech National Agency for international education and research, Ukrainian representatives from the Ministry and from the HE sector.

This second edition of the report on the best practices of Alliances in cooperating with Ukraine aims to highlight the gaps, opportunities and challenges that Alliances are facing in cooperating in a structured and sustainable way with Ukrainian HEIs. Key initiatives, strategies and experimentations are presented as examples of answers provided to some of the needs listed by their counterparts in Ukraine and to the priorities set by policy-makers. This report does not pretend to cover all aspects of academic cooperation with Ukraine and all Alliances' examples, and it will be updated when needed. It is a working document with evidence-based solutions showcasing that Alliances are ready-to-use tools to network and strategically plan for a common European future, in case more support can be granted.

The report will provide the reader with some background information about the updated state of higher education involvement in Europe in solidarity with Ukraine, and a review of the needs analyses and the key policy priorities drawn by Ukraine and the EU, as well as Member States, in this matter. It goes on presenting existing rationales, results and obstacles at the heart of the Alliances' experimentations, and some directions based on lessons learned, to help Alliances structure their strategic long-term planning, as it is discussed in the FOREU4ALL Community of Practice's topical group "Cooperation with Ukraine". It ends with recommendations addressed to EU policy-makers.

By supporting Alliances in building such strategic partnerships, the EU can foster both values-based international academic cooperation and position Alliances as solid magnets attracting academic opportunities, providing a competitive advantage and resilience to higher education in Europe. The report ends with the Open letter signed by 35 alliances calling for such support.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report provides the reader with up-to-date information on the involvement of HEIs in Europe and European universities alliances, in solidarity with Ukrainian higher education and research in the context of the full-scale Russian invasion since February 2022. It highlights:

- **Numerous direct, intense individual and institutional academic contacts** allowing for scientific collaboration and needs assessment, based on long-standing cooperation between HEIs in Europe and the Ukrainian higher education and research, or on new platforms;
- The **very impressive courage, determination, creativity and resilience of students, academic colleagues and researchers in Ukraine**, despite terror attacks against civilians and infrastructures;
- The key dimension of the **promotion of EU values across the 65 Alliances' missions** representing 570 HEIs in Europe since the launch of the first generation of Alliances in 2019;
- The **unity of action and high level of commitment of Alliances and their partner universities** to initiate action in solidarity with Ukraine;
- The **commitment expressed by a majority of Alliances to respond to the request of long-term cooperation with Ukrainian partners either by welcoming one or more Ukrainian HEIs into their integrated consortia** - 35 Alliances have done so to date, **or by strategically planning via projects**.

The report highlights a series of **challenges** limiting the capacity of Alliances to act:

- **Until today Ukrainian HEIs are not eligible to the Alliances funding** under Erasmus+;
- While substantial European and national funding have been made available to support students and staff from Ukraine since 2023 and develop institutional cooperation, **Alliances and Ukrainian partners have to engage in multiple, time-consuming calls with limited time frame and impact**;
- **Alliances miss the strategic opportunity to develop, with neighbouring countries aiming to EU accession, a common research and innovation capacity** by not having this international dimension defined among their objectives and no dedicated funding schemes to support such goals.

The report supports the following recommendations:

- We **welcome the European Commission's MFF proposal 2028-2034 to dedicate 100 bn euro to the reconstruction and modernisation of Ukraine and to support the Eastern regions, and the enhanced support proposed to Ukraine's integration into the EEA in Erasmus+ 2028-34**;
- **We call for more national support in the Member States comprising an Alliance's dimension and for national and European funding to become more synchronised**;
- We **support the European Parliament's draft report** on a "New vision for the European universities alliances" that "welcomes **value-based initiatives** such as the cooperation in solidarity with Ukraine and the role of alliances in preparing for accession with Eastern neighbourhood countries";
- **Reconstruction of Ukraine needs coordination**: we support EUA recommendation (2023) on **inter-institutional collaboration as a key success factor for (long-term) continued support for Ukrainian higher education**, and we recommend to use the **bottom-up capacity of Alliances to network, connect and support Ukrainian higher education and research while growing together for a more innovative and resilient Europe**;
- **Support EUA recommendation (2025) on improving crisis resilience and response in the frame of Erasmus+** (recommendation 11), with an ambitious programme to "support scholars at risk and support at-risk students", in line with the "**Choose Europe for science**" initiative;
- For the Erasmus+ **work programme 2026-2027**, we ask for setting the cooperation with Ukraine among the possible criteria for Alliances' goals, and to open calls helping in this process e.g., to **support the appointment of Ukraine liaison officers within Alliances and the management of existing strategic partnerships** in order to integrating Ukrainian HEIs into European innovative practices *by and for* networks of EU HEIs, in line with the policy priorities and expected outcomes in education and research of Ukraine and the EU; in **Horizon Europe**, we call for an increased access to funding for joint research projects with Ukrainian partners (individuals, institutions); in HE and research, we recommend allowing for the creation of **structural inclusion mechanisms**.

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BACKGROUND INFORMATION

a.Higher education in solidarity with Ukraine

b.Why are we as Alliances involved?

c.Choose Europe for Science

Higher education institutions in Ukraine and in the EU, including Alliances, have enhanced their cooperation and they are ready to actively contribute to the new EU policy priorities to “Choose Europe for Science” today, and to the next MFF proposal to enhance Ukraine’s integration into the EEA, in order to achieve a more resilient academic world.

HIGHER EDUCATION IN SOLIDARITY WITH UKRAINE

The higher education sector in Ukraine has shown an extraordinary resilience despite the huge losses, primarily people, and the major disruptions in planning because of the full-scale war:

-1,5 million students, 30.000 foreign students, 115.000 academic staff (decrease of 5000 University teachers while the number of students increased by almost 100.000 in 2024, as full-time students have a deferral from conscription into the army). The forecast for applicants to HEIs looks pessimistic with 150.000 less students at schools registered in 2023.

-Teaching and learning process from shelters, frontlines and abroad (extreme learning and teaching conditions, extreme stress, burnouts among students, administrative and academic staff).

-Human losses among students, academic and administrative staff, and severe trauma. Many academic staff has left abroad and it has become essential to bringing them back or keeping them connected and avoiding greater brain drain.

-27% of HEIs in Ukraine have been damaged or completely destroyed, in particular in Zhytomyr (100%), Chernihiv (75%), Donetsk (72%), Kharkiv (62%), Mykolayiv (55%), Odessa (45%), Luhansk (43%). In June 2025, UNESCO has reported more than 500 damaged cultural sites, of which 18 libraries.

-34 HEIs have been temporarily relocated (Mariupol, Donetsk, Luhansk regions, Zaporizhzhia and Kherson regions), in most cases moving the administration, the accounting department and several key employees to another city and usually hosted by another HEI, while maintaining teaching and learning remotely, regardless of the physical location.

-Limited resources - budget cuts affect salaries, infrastructure and research.

-Electricity cuts, no heating, sirens, long-term blackouts.

-Huge challenge to organise enrolment campaigns.

According to EUA Trends 2024, **80% of HEIs in Europe declared having initiated solidarity measures** for supporting Ukrainian students, with half of the respondents doing so under special conditions such as grants, reduced fees, etc. 41% of them hosted academic staff from Ukraine. 29% reported having enhanced their existing partnerships with Ukrainian institutions, and 28% have established new ones.

The EUA Trends 2024 report is built upon the report in 2023 by Osvit Analytics and the K. Adenauer Stiftung in Kyiv. The report noted that by 2022 all national agencies under Erasmus+ created a separated webpage dedicated to supporting Ukrainian students and researchers, and the same was true for European universities which published information.

By the end of 2023, Ukraine has had the biggest number of mobility projects funded under Erasmus+ among 144 partner countries all over the world ([link](#)). **It has been grounded on 30 years of experience in Tempus and Erasmus projects with Ukrainian higher education.** As a result, the resilience of higher education in Ukraine has been reinforced thanks to international cooperation (table 1). According to the most updated data collected by the **Erasmus+ office for Ukraine**, Erasmus+ funding schemes covered nearly 12.000 international mobilities for Ukrainian Universities staff and students, 10 virtual exchange projects in higher education and youth, 13 Erasmus mundus joint master programmes design and implementation, 184 Cooperation partnerships projects with 50 education institutions, 8 projects of Alliances for innovation with Ukrainian industries and HEIs as partners, 47 projects on capacity building in higher education at 103 education institutions, and 256 Jean Monnet projects (European studies) with 72 HEIs.

Table 1: Number of Ukrainian HEIs involved in a Erasmus + funded project(Source: Erasmus + for Ukraine (September 2025))

ACTIONS - 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025	Funded year	5 years				
Calls for Proposals	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	Total
KA1 Learning mobility for Youth projects / grants	222	345	347	264	102	1280 /7 896
KA 151. Accredited organisations individual grants for Ukrainians						2024
KA152.Youth Exchanges projects / grants	114	182	193	150	59	698 /3999
KA153. Youth Workers projects / grants	101	154	140	102	40	537 /1532
KA154.YouthParticipation projects/grants	7	9	14	12	3	45/341
KA171.International (Credit) Mobility projects/ grants	140 / 4248		137 / 3925	105 / 3508	120/	502/ 11 681
KA121.Mobility for VET						
KA 183.Virtual Exchanges	2	1	3	4		10
KA2 Cooperation between organisations						
Cooperation Projects in Education and Youth (CPs):	21	29	68	53	4	172
KA220-YOU. Cooperation Projects in Youth	8	13	21	13	2	57
KA220-SCH. Cooperation Projects in School Education	2	3	5	1		11
KA220-VET. Cooperation Projects in VET	3	1	6	7		17
KA220-HED. Cooperation Projects in Higher Education	3	8	32	30	2	75
KA220-ADU. Cooperation Projects in Adult Education	5	1	4	2		12
Cooperation Projects in Sport&NFPSE	2	3	10	6		21
KA236. ENGO – Education and training				1		1
KA236. ENGO – Youth			1	2		3
KA234.Alliances for Innovations	2	3	4	1		10
KA238.Centres of Vocational Excellence			2	3		5
KA2 European Universities Alliances	NA	2	19	12		33
KA231. Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Projects (full/associated partners)	1	1	2	6	4	14
KA231. Erasmus Mundus Design Measures (grantholders/partners)	0	2	1	0		3
KA231. Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Scholarships	29	52	20	20	28	149
KA211. Capacity Building in Higher Education	NA	13	20	14	22	69
KA233. Capacity Building in VET	NA	2	1	7	6	16
KA2. Capacity Building for Sport	NA	NA	NA	7	4	11
KA237.Capacity Building for Youth	NA	NA	NA	9	8	17
Jean Monnet	38	93	90	35		256

In addition, 14 Ukrainian HEIs are coordinating a Capacity-building project, and a consortium of 10 Ukrainian universities with 6 European full university partners has been set to create a digital open university in Ukraine. **In total, 227 UA HEIs, 3 VET institutions and 58 other organisations are involved into nearly 2000 projects.** But investing in international cooperation also generated new issues of dedicating sufficient time and staff, extra workload, staff safety, delays in project activities, etc.

Several actions are relevant in relation to Alliances' activities. The 8 projects of **Alliances for innovation** with Ukrainian industries and Ukrainian HEIs as partners benefit from a grant of 4 million euro per project and have goals in line with the **Union of skills**. Another focus is on the 13 selected **Erasmus mundus joint programmes with a Ukrainian partner**: from 2021 to 2024, 6 Ukrainian HEIs applied for preparatory projects to bring a joint programme to the point of being ready to operate as an accredited joint degree, and 3 were selected; 24 Ukrainian HEIs (15 in 2024 alone) applied to a Joint master awarding scholarships to master students and 10 were selected. This contributes to building experience in operationalising **joint degrees** according to EU standards, an experience already initiated during the previous funding period (16 selected, 2014-2020).

Other data worth considering are the current 250+ **Jean Monnet actions** in Ukraine, not least because the number of selected actions has more than doubled compared to 2014-2020 (256 versus 115; applications have had similar 10-15% success rate). This funding scheme has been launched by the European Commission since 1989 to support academic research in European integration. It has empowered scholars and HEIs in the EU and in third countries to develop teaching, research and outreach activities in the field of European studies, with the aim of making *“European integration not just an economic project, but a concern of everyone in society. Europe [is] a project for future generations and as such, students [have] to be engaged more than anyone else”*. Before moving to DG EAC, Jean Monnet actions were managed by the EC unit for Youth and Universities (DG Press and information) ([link](#)).

From the 1970s, this unit received queries from the U.S., Japan, and also Poland, Hungary and China, allowing for direct contacts and academic support when a “non-relations” policy was in place. Only given access to the Jean Monnet programme in 1993, Poland had already 6 Chairs by 1994, providing training and expertise that was particularly decisive for policy-makers in preparing for EU accession. Since 2001, Ukrainian HEIs are extremely active in these kind of actions.

The Jean Monnet programme is considered as an example for good practice in inter-university cooperation, based on solidarity. Following this example, higher education level of actions could play an important role in developing a capacity by HEIs to offer a scientific-based better understanding of the EU and Ukraine, and bring them to the widest audience in European and Ukrainian societies. As an example, in May 2025, **4EU+ and EUniWell** have jointly organised a conference about the development of Ukrainian studies in Europe and the support for Ukraine’s current accession procedure to the EU at the **University of Warsaw** ([link](#)).

More broadly, this **highlights the relevance of the cooperation between HEIs in the EU and with accession countries**. Alliances may become good tools and a significant number of Alliances have in fact partner universities located in potential or official candidate countries (table 2). In relation to Ukraine, 32 Alliances have welcomed one or more Ukrainian HEIs and more Alliances are in close connection with one or more Ukrainian partners, supported via national and European funded cooperation projects. In the Community of Practice FOREU4ALL, one out of the 20 thematic groups is dedicated to “Cooperation with Ukraine” and 45 Alliances are represented.

Table 2: Alliances having one or more partners in one of the candidate countries distributed according to the estimation of the future waves of enlargement. Source: European policy centre (2025) and own compilation of data

WAVE 1 (potentially from 2027)	
Ukraine	Arqus, EU GREEN, UNIC, ENHANCE, UNIVERSEH, Aurora, FILM EU, T4EU, E3UDRES2, STARS EU, EC2U, EUniWell, RUN-EU, ULYSSEUS, UNITA, EUPeace, INT.TUNE, UREKA, COLOURS, NEOLAIa, HEROES, PIONEER, UNINOVIS, OpenEU, KreativEU, BAUHAUS4EU, SUNRISE, EUonAIR, Across, EMERGE, ACE2EU, ARTEMIS
Montenegro	ULYSSEUS
Moldova	none
WAVE 2	
Albania	E3UDRES2, STARS EU, BAUHAUS4EU, UNINOVIS
North Macedonia	COLOURS, ACE2EU, CHALLENGE EU
WAVE 3	
Bosnia-Herzegovina	EUPeace (2 partners), Across, SUNRISE
Serbia	EUGLOH, Circle U., INT.TUNE
Türkiye	EELISA, EUPeace, NeurotechEU, UNIC, KreativEU
Kosovo	E3UDRES2, EUPeace

INVOLVEMENT OF OUR EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES ALLIANCES: WHY?

The **Communication on the European Strategy for Universities** (2022) highlighted several missions to be pursued by European universities alliances: strengthen the European dimension in higher education and research, consolidate universities as lighthouses of our European way of life, empower universities as key actors of change in the twin green and digital transitions, reinforce universities as drivers of Europe's global role and leadership. To achieve it, Alliances are asked to build their own transnational capacities on the basis of a wide geographical coverage and institutional diversity to allow for seamless mobility of students and staff, implement innovative joint educational programmes, cooperate with society and economy, develop the research and innovation dimension, and work as testbeds and share outcomes for the wider higher education system. After 5 years of action by the first ones, Alliances have many innovative experimentations in cross-border cooperation to share, as PPMI evidenced in the [report](#) released in 2025.

Today, there are 65 Alliances representing 570 HEIs across the EU and beyond. In the Alliances' long-term missions, European values come first. Freedom, human rights, democracy, solidarity, openness, excellence, inclusiveness are our key reference points. Alliances such as **EUPeace** have as core mission to "provide tomorrow's citizens with the skills, knowledge, and experience to cultivate Peace, Justice, and inclusive societies". For some Alliances such as **Aurora**, the solidarity cooperation with **Karazin University in Kharkiv** started in 2019, before the Alliance got funded. As soon as the brutal Russian full-scale invasion initiated in February 2022, all Alliances positioned themselves [in solidarity with Ukraine](#). From 2022, cooperation within an Alliance has been formalised with 2 Ukrainian HEIs joining Alliances, rising to 18 in 2023 and additional 15 HEIs of Ukraine joining 9 new Alliances in 2024.

Together with Ukrainian HEIs, originating from the long-standing links of some of their members or new connections in relation to the European universities initiative, Alliances have aimed at getting regular updates about the needs of colleagues, students and institutions in Ukraine. Many solidarity actions have followed, as this report illustrates. Based on information from the ground, cross-alliances peer learning has developed, allowing for a better understanding of the different national realities in assisting Ukraine across the EU. In June 2022, a joint statement on "the twinning partnership between Ukrainian and European universities" was supported by 25 Alliances and the Ukrainian higher education sector ([link](#)). It was followed by the significant rise in the number of Ukrainian HEIs joining an Alliance, increased visibility and political support, and it created new challenges, as Ukrainian HEIs have not been made eligible to European universities alliances' funds in the Erasmus+ programme (2021-27).

This cross-alliances work has become formalised recently within the **FOREU4ALL Community of Practice** for an enhanced mutual support in developing knowledge and tools, and plan strategic long-term cooperation. By July 2025, **49 Alliances** have nominated at least one representative to participate to this topical group, all experienced in cooperating with one or more Ukrainian HEIs. Joint statements have communicated a shared expression of solidarity since 2022, and 2 cross-alliances initiatives were coordinated to ask for political and financial support to the EU and Member States. The most recent one can be found at the end of this report.

CHOOSE EUROPE FOR SCIENCE

6.5 million people who had to flee their home in Ukraine have been welcomed in another part of the country (2 million) or in the EU, primarily in Poland and in Germany (1 million people each). In May 2025, the ratio of temporary protection beneficiaries from Ukraine relative to the population was the highest in Czechia (34.3 per 1 000 persons), ahead of Poland (26.9) and Estonia (24.9). In Poland in the first days of the war, HEIs took a major role in organising shelters for refugees and solidarity campaigns. For instance, the **University of Gdańsk (SEA-EU)**, in addition to speaking out against the war, among other things operated as a logistics centre for donations with 400 trucks leaving for Ukraine, thanks to dozens of student and staff volunteers collecting donations and preparing the parcels, and donated 2 dormitories for 2 years to the local authorities to welcome refugees.

As part of **SEA-EU**, the then 6 partners funded the participation of specialists from the **I.I. Mechnikov National University of Odesa** in the alliance's activities, focusing on academic solidarity. During the conference "Focus on Ukraine" in May 2022, a PhD candidate from **Kharkiv National University** stated that "it is very important for us that we come to Poland not as refugees, but as academics. It gives us a sense of dignity. We can do more than just try to survive" ([link](#)).

In European countries, there has been a **tradition for support mechanisms towards scholars at risk**. **Inspireurope project** has built a network across Europe to facilitate the cooperation (e.g., mapping) between such initiatives and programmes, like the SAFE project that has offered 60 fellowships up to 24 months for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers of any non-EU country to work at a research institution in the EU ([link](#)). In France, the PAUSE (Collège de France) and THEMIS (Maison des sciences de l'homme) programmes are examples of scholarships for emergency stays, to which the **University of Strasbourg** has been actively taking part ([link](#), [link](#)).

Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) is a support mechanism for talented scholars (early-career researchers) which is funded by Horizon Europe. It includes an instrument to support scholars at risk, combining the search for excellence with the respect of European fundamental values. Since September 2022, 175 researchers have received a fellowship grant from **MSCA4Ukraine** between 6 months and 2 years and support to re-establish in Ukraine when conditions permit. Available support allows to maintain links with their research and innovation communities, carry out research placements and develop new projects. There is no forthcoming call for applications.

European research council (ERC) has appealed to its grantees to provide temporary employment to refugee researchers and support staff from Ukraine ([link](#)) + **ERC4Ukraine** ([link](#)).

Following recent events in the United States of America, the definition of “scholars at risk” has been extended to scholars not only facing a war context but also to include scholars under attack because of attack on the role of science in society and against academic freedom. In May 2025 at Sorbonne University, the **European Commission** has announced the **Choose Europe for science** initiative with an increased support (500 million euro) to talented international scholars, coming from all over the world and with a focus on scholars coming from conflict zones. This initiative is launching pilot grants offering long-term positions under MSCA, and aims at simplifying the application procedures on project management and visa.

The EU goal is to promote **values-based cooperation**, providing a “safe haven” for researchers at risk that shall be a way forward to foster EU competitiveness. The **European Parliament** has a longstanding commitment towards the protection of academic freedom as a core EU value and has set a monitoring tool. On 24 June 2025, the CULT committee members adopted the report on “**A new vision for the European universities alliances**”, defining **their role as drivers “for academic excellence and EU values”** and welcoming “**value-based initiatives such as the cooperation in solidarity with Ukraine and the role of alliances in preparing for accession with Eastern neighbourhood countries**” (amendment 141, adopted).

In July 2025, **UNESCO** has released an **Action Plan for Sciences “Building a robust science ecosystem in Ukraine”**, underscoring the central role of science in Ukraine’s recovery and reconstruction process, and listing a series of concrete measures. Among those measures, short-term priority actions are defined to stabilise Ukraine’s research sector, provide remote access to critical research infrastructure and ensure continuity of research work in a crisis situation. Research grants are envisaged as pilots. In close cooperation with the **National Research foundation of Ukraine**, it is planned to create a mechanism for accelerated grant funding and emergency fellowships to support the livelihoods of researchers affected by the war.

For HEIs and Alliances in Europe, from speaking out against the war and initiating solidarity activities towards Ukraine to the defence of academic freedom like under the MSCA and other programmes, there has been an increasing awareness of their **responsibility as compass for democracy** (e.g., EUA trends 2024).

The **Choose Europe for Science** approach is **meaningful to Alliances as they can offer an attractive and efficient European-wide network to talented scholars around the globe, share the cost of hosting the researchers and infrastructures and allow the free circulation across the continent, while staying true to their core values**. It is **meaningful to Alliances in relation to Ukraine**, too: in addition to attracting talented scholars, it will contribute to **making Europe more resilient by developing excellence and competences in areas such as security, preparedness, economic recovery, green and digital (educational) transition, supporting active citizenship and peace-building, preparing for EU accession and making the Eastern border of the EU more stable and safer**.

POLICY PRIORITIES

a.Ukrainian authorities

b.European institutions and Member states

Since February 2022, policy-makers have been quick in defining new priorities for supporting the higher education and research in Ukraine. However so far Ukrainian higher education institutions cannot benefit from Alliances' funding schemes.

PRIORITIES OF UKRAINIAN AUTHORITIES

Ukrainian recent reforms in higher education and research:

Two days before the start of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russia, the **Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine** adopted the **Strategy for the HE development Ukraine – 2032**, in line with European integration prospects and EHEA principles. In 2023, the reform of learning pathway was approved, expanding the opportunities of students to form individualised learning pathways. In addition, the reform has dealt with increasing the autonomy of HEIs in the development of interdisciplinary educational programmes and the recognition of non-formal education. In 2024, the reform included expanding the rights of student self-governance bodies and ensuring the rights of students. The **law of Ukraine on academic integrity** was adopted in first reading in 2024. An **autonomy experiment** (organisational, personnel, financial) has been launched in the same year and is ongoing. Last but not least, the **Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine** (MESoU) has called for the **modernisation and transformation of the HEIs network**, made of 217 state universities in 2023. In all these years, **cultural diplomacy** has been central, including academic areas (e.g., promotion of Ukrainian studies).

Higher education priorities under Martial law:

the Ukrainian Government requires that all efforts shall go first to armed forces, security for higher education communities, European integration (higher education reforms, internationalisation, academic contribution), re-establishment of classroom trainings in remote regions, digital education, new educational programmes (media literacy, cyber security, post trauma and mental health, resilience studies, peace education, Ukrainian studies), special study programmes for veterans and reintegration in society, return of people fleeing from war (internally and abroad) ([link](#)).

MESoU has made clear recommendations in line with the preparation to EU accession in the **priorities for Erasmus+ projects**: European integration of Ukraine in curricula, training interpreters and translators, higher education for the post-war recovery, inclusive and innovative higher education area for the third mission of Universities, individual learning pathways in higher education, English as a lingua franca of higher education, pedagogical education reform (teacher), open science in higher education institutions.

Ukraine recovery conference, Rome, July 2025: the annual event coordinating the international support for the recovery, reform and modernisation of Ukraine, has addressed the human dimension as a key element of the prosperity of the country: "build forward". Education provides freedom to people, knowledge and skills to ease the reintegration of veterans and displaced people. As most of the displaced people are minors or in age of initial or life-long learning (Graph 1), there are urgent needs for HEIs of Ukraine in operating efficiently to welcome them back and cooperate with HEIs in Europe.

Graph 1: People with EU temporary status from Ukraine by age

Note: EU total excluding:
France - data for minors generally not included.
EU total for March 2025 calculated by using latest available Portuguese data from December 2024.
Source: Eurostat (migr_asypsm)

Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Temporary_protection_for_persons_fleeing_Ukraine_-_monthly_statistics (June 2025)

PRIORITIES OF EUROPEAN INSTITUTIONS

Ever since the beginning of the war, the EU has stood with Ukraine, condemning Russia's war of aggression and holding it accountable, and by becoming the largest donor (150 billion euro) to assist Ukraine and its people. A new financing instrument (**Ukraine facility**) of up to 50 billion euro was created and the new Commission's proposal is to double it in the next MFF (2028-2034).

More specifically on education and research, from March 2022, the **European Commission's** recommendation has been for the "highest flexibility possible in implementing projects towards Ukrainian students and HE staff", both for mobility and capacity-building or partnership cooperation. 200 million euros have been granted in addition to the 2023 Erasmus+ budget (of which 100 million for partnership actions) to support Ukrainian learners and staff currently displaced in the EU and retain their links with Ukraine, and to answer the consequences of the war, in particular to provide assistance to the relocated universities. Several actions that have been focused on Ukraine were launched: Horizon4Ukraine for research and innovation projects, MSCA4Ukraine (doctoral and postdoctoral candidates), ERA4Ukraine (all EU support available [here](#)).

Among HEIs in Europe, according to EUA (2025, graph 2), there is an overall positive feedback about the relevance of Erasmus+ in supporting Ukrainian universities and students, but a long-term approach to welcome students is requested by 36% of respondents. 39% of respondents asked for a programme to support academics from Ukraine. The EU provides support at the ministerial level via the participation of the team of national experts on higher education reform in working groups working on legislative changes in preparation to EU accession, in relation to the Bologna process and the Ukraine facility plan.

Graph 2: HEIs' assessment of the relevance of Erasmus+ to support Ukrainian universities and students (EUA, 2025)

In addition, currently the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Ukraine, the Mission of Ukraine to the EU and the National Erasmus+ office in Ukraine are holding consultations with the DG EAC on **expanding opportunities for Ukrainian organisations, using the example of special support to the countries of the Western Balkans.**

The **European Parliament** is one of the strongest advocates for Ukraine accession to the EU and has adopted many resolutions calling for military and financial assistance to Ukraine. In a report on the EU's Common Security and Defense Policy adopted in April 2025, deputies condemned any attempts to blackmail Ukraine into surrendering to the Russian aggressor ([here](#)). Mid-July 2025, the **Council of the EU** adopted the 18th package of sanctions against Russia.

On a regular basis, the **Committee of the Regions** has been recalling that 20% of the Ukraine facility plan is for the civil society including education & research. The **European Alliance of Cities and Regions for the reconstruction of Ukraine** has been launched calling for an easy engagement mechanism and twinning strategic partnerships ([link](#)). Another important initiative was the adoption by the Council of Ministers (**Council of Europe**) of the action plan for Ukraine 2023-2026 "**Promoting democratic culture and human rights education in higher education institutions**" in 2022.

PRIORITIES OF EU MEMBER STATES

EU Member states' uses of European funds:

As reported by EJA (2025), there has been significant countries' variations in the use of Erasmus+ funding to support students from Ukraine: *"Finland, Ireland and Sweden received relatively high numbers of Ukrainian students supported by Erasmus+. Geographical closeness to Ukraine contributed to the extensive deployment of Erasmus+ funding in Czechia, Lithuania and Slovakia, but, on the other hand, not so much in Poland and Romania. (...) In the survey, institutions cited various reasons for not using this funding, including the availability of more generous and easier-to-handle national funds (e.g., Austria, Germany, Poland and Norway). In addition, other issues may have prevented stronger participation: for example, in Denmark, national authorities insisted on reciprocity of exchanges, and German universities mentioned losing places for outgoing students as a motive not to participate, or at least not to commit too many places"*.

In addition, top 5 programme countries in **Capacity-Building** for higher education (CBHE) with Ukraine are Germany, Spain, Italy, Poland, and Estonia. Last but not least, the **EU, Lithuania, Denmark and Sweden** launched the **Ukraine2EU** initiative in April 2025 to support Ukraine's path to EU accession and strengthen its integration efforts via strategic guidance and expert support to Ukrainian authorities ([link](#)).

Poland - NAWA "Solidarity with Ukraine - European universities" (2022-2024):

For many universities in Europe national support has been a way to assist Ukraine, also in relation with alliances' strategic development. Poland is a key example because of the large number of people who have been welcomed from Ukraine, the wide human solidarity expressed by the Polish society and the support provided by the national authorities.

In particular, the Polish academic exchange agency (NAWA) experienced strong interest and intense participation of Polish universities that were a member of an alliance with the initiative "Solidarity with Ukraine - European universities". Dedicated not to individuals but to institutions, this initiative, running from September 2022 to the end of 2024, provided 18 million złoty (4.5 million euro) to activities organised by 23 Polish HEIs, benefitting to 77 partner universities from Ukraine and delivering more than 2600 mobilities.

In the case of the **University Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań** (AMU), in 2023 and 2024, nearly 50 summer schools and accompanying events and logistics, involving more than 1300 participants have been organised, together with some **EPICUR** partners. Among them were the event on Alliances' cooperation in solidarity with Ukraine at the European Parliament in Strasbourg with the participation of the Vice President of the European Parliament Ms. Ewa Kopacz in March 2024, and a discussion on the future of Ukrainian universities in Poznań attended by more than 60 rectors and pro-rectors of Ukrainian universities in October 2024 ([link](#)). AMU benefitted from 2 NAWA grants and one by the National Center for Research and Development.

Other alliances' examples based on the funding provided by NAWA "Solidarity with Ukraine - European universities" (2022-2024, [link](#), [link bis](#)):

- **SEA-EU's conference "Focus on Ukraine"** took place at **University of Gdańsk** in May 2022 and was selected #1 by NAWA in 2023 for allowing in-depth and timely discussions bringing a shift of action in supporting academic cooperation during and after the war, with **MESoU**
- **Unite!** welcomed 7 Ukrainian universities in 2 satellite projects in 2023 and 2024 in the field of the green transition led by **Wrocław Tech** (green standards in engineering and technical sciences, Green campus model, summerschool, pilot on micro-credentials style training for Ukrainian HEIs), field study tours in partner universities at **TU Graz** and **TU Darmstadt**.
- **CIVICA** participated in 2023 and 2024 under the "CIVICA for Ukraine" project managed by **SGH Warsaw School of Economics**, with more than 200 mobilities of students, PhD, faculty and staff from Ukrainian universities in all CIVICA partner universities, who took part in joint activities (e.g., study visit to Brussels, CIVICA Ambassadors Forum on Recovery and Modernisation of Ukraine, International Leadership Training for early career researchers, etc)
- **FORTHEM** organised 70 short-term academic mobilities to offer opportunities for academic, cultural and linguistic immersion and matchmaking during FORTHEM events, in particular in **University of Opole**. The alliance delivered online workshops and hybrid cooperation models via the FORTHEM Labs, using virtual mobility. Topics like multilingualism, digital innovation and European identity-building were covered
- **ENHANCE** has had its activities complemented in 2024 with **Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute** and **Lviv Polytechnic National University** thanks to the grant received by **Gdańsk University of Technology**, in particular on digital education, smart cities and Enhance's sustainable week. In May 2025, the ENHANCE taskforce for Ukraine organised an online event to explore innovative projects for Ukraine's sustainable reconstruction ([link](#)).
- **ECIU University** 12 month projects (twice) aimed at bringing 10 Ukrainian universities closer to the European universities initiative and was supported by **Lodz University of Technology**. It gave the opportunity to participants to enhance teaching and learning methods, such as challenge based learning and micro-credentials and foster stronger connections with **ECIU**
- **EU GREEN:** The [INTERACT](#) and [INTERACT 2.0](#) projects aimed to strengthen international cooperation between the Alliance and Ukrainian universities. Through activities like study visits, research internships, summer schools, and consortium meetings, they fostered scientific collaboration and supported the integration of Ukrainian HEIs into European academic networks. 21 research internships and 32 study visits were conducted (INTERACT 2.0 added 2 more Ukrainian partners, 23 more internships). Ukrainian students actively participated in EU GREEN activities, including blended intensive programmes and summer schools (e.g., "Sustainable State of Nature"). It was based on previous long-standing experiences in EU-funded projects (e.g., **University of Parma** TEMPUS projects and Erasmus KA projects, still ongoing). Once the Alliance was launched in 2023, research clusters included Ukrainian researchers, with online meetings, research internships, and participation to staff weeks on international projects' management. BIP on "Soil protection and management of degraded and industrial lands" was organized by **Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences**.
- **ERUA**, under the leadership of **SWPS University**, developed workshops for 7 Ukrainian universities on academic innovations in the frame of the **ERUA Academic Innovation Laboratory**, as well as a series of workshops concerning psychological support ([link](#))
- **4EU+** organised online training sessions on key areas such as intercultural communication, artificial intelligence, career planning, translations, well-being and digital education. The Alliance conducted specialized workshops for librarians and hosted a summer school titled "Intercultural Communication in Diplomacy and Public Administration" at the **University of Warsaw**. Ukrainian students were granted access to online courses available to all students within the Alliance, further enhancing their educational opportunities during challenging times.

BEST PRACTICES OF ALLIANCES

a. Rationale, results and challenges based on own-funded, national and EU funding schemes

b. Towards strategic planning

Higher education institutions and Alliances have experienced cooperation with Ukrainian partners in many ways and academic fields. This section shows cases illustrating these experiences, their achievements and limitations so far, and draws key conclusions and recommendations for an efficient strategic planning.

BEST PRACTICES FROM HEIS (OWN FUNDED INITIATIVES)

Rationale of initiatives based on own funds or volunteering from academic & students communities:

- Develop direct student and academic contacts for grassroots initiatives and capacity-building projects, based on own-conducted needs analyses, such as: European rectors' Women Association (**EWORA**) did in 2023 a survey of Ukrainian universities about their needs and how universities globally could help ([link](#)), that was used by the **ERUA** alliance to reflect about its strategy; **CIVICA** produced regular reports on the challenges and needs, also from the students' perspective ([link](#)); **4EU+** did online consultations with Ukrainian universities to understand their specific needs and expectations before starting planning the NAWA funded actions (see previous section);
- Starting with students and faculty connections across partners and towards Ukraine: for instance, **Science4Ukraine** is a community group of volunteer students and research scientists from academic institutions in Europe and around the world. Their mission is to collect and disseminate information about support opportunities at the university, national, and international level for graduate students and researchers directly affiliated to a Ukraine academic institution. Other students' initiatives are [ESN Ukraine](#), Student unions ([Austria](#), [European student union](#)), [Unissued diplomas exhibition](#), [Model European Union](#) in Strasbourg, etc. The **European network of Higher Arts Education (ELIA)** is a platform to initiatives and resources for students and scholars in the Arts.
- **Offer a membership to an alliance as a sign of solidarity and sense of sharing a common future**, with immediate impact in terms of access to several partners, visibility of the alliances and testing or observing some practices (education, research, governance).

Results:

Efficiency in providing immediate assistance, from material and humanitarian assistance (survival kits, generators, laptops, servers, software, simulators... welcoming pupils and students, scholars, accommodation and fees reduction, psychological help) to academic support to allow for continuity:

- Example 1: **Silesian university in Opava** (Czechia) - from spontaneous academic hospitality to the involvement of Ukrainian partners into research activities within **STARS EU**:

"The Russian army fired 30 different missiles and drones at our city [Mykolayiv] every day. When you hide from them, you forget your name and feel only fear. In the morning, when you wake up, you find out what has been demolished and destroyed. (...) The final straw for me was the damage to the infrastructure when our great city was left completely without water. I guess that was the moment I started looking for opportunities to leave. We had no relatives or friends abroad, so it was clear that this trip would be at our own risk, responsibility, but also full of fear. (...) I wanted to pursue a job based on my education. I wrote several letters to different universities. I had no hope at all and decided to put everything in the hands of my destiny. If I hadn't found such an opportunity, I certainly wouldn't have left. Literally a moment after sending my letters, I had a reply from the Dean of the School of Business Administration in Karviná, Silesian University in Opava. There have been very few miracles in my life, so I immediately grabbed this opportunity. I had a video interview with the dean and when asked: "When can you come?" I replied with precision and certainty, "Tomorrow!" A few days after the interview I was already in Karviná." ([link](#))

- Example 2: **Mykolas Romeris University** (MRU, Lithuania) is a member of **ERUA** alliance and has prioritized initiatives that ensured continuity and inclusivity in Ukrainian academic pursuits; while doing it, MRU has made sure it can regularly share it with partners in the alliance that are also actively engaged in assisting Ukraine, such as **Viadrina University** (Germany), **Paris 8 University**:

-fundraising of scholarship programmes and design of flexible tuition fees for Ukrainian students to minimize financial barriers and encourage enrolment, scholars programmes dedicated to Ukrainian academics, offering temporary teaching and research positions at MRU;

-MRU Senate declared the year of 2023 the Ukrainian Freedom Year and encouraged academic staff to include Ukrainian partners in projects, in international professional organizations and networks, and in preparing joint publications, trainings and events;

- From March 2022, MRU shared its premises to host "Gravita Schola" for 500 pupils escaping the war;
- in 2024 MRU launched an initiative Lawyers4Ukraine aimed to mobilise and activate Lithuanian lawyers to support the injured children in war and provide them with medical treatment in Lithuania.
- Example 3: **BAUHAUS4EU** is an alliance in the field of heritage that started in 2024 including 2 Ukrainian partners and that is about signing the Global coalition of Ukrainian studies. At the university level, some partners such as **Université Lumière Lyon 2** (France) have actively participated to the PAUSE programme, with 2 Ukrainian scholars undergoing their research now.
- Example 4: **ULYSSEUS** in applied sciences aims at developing joint digital education and research in engineering manufacturing with 3 Ukrainian partners. For instance, at the **Technical University of Košice** (Slovakia), earlier joint research project funded by the Slovakian research and development agency and the Ministry of education and science of Ukraine led to joint publications with a researcher from **Sumy State University**, and to a series of academic exchanges, with joint programmes for virtual mobility (e.g., "advanced manufacturing: innovations in materials and technologies"), with **Poznań University of Technology** (Poland) and International association for technological development and innovations. In June 2025, the 8th international conference on "design, simulation, manufacturing: the innovation exchange" was organised by the 3 universities.
- Example 5: **35 Alliances have welcomed an Ukrainian HEI as full or associated members** (table 2). In 2022, **Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv** (KNU) has become a full member of **EUniWell** and started academic collaborations based on alliance's seed funding. **SEA-EU** has been considering this option with the partner **I.I. Mechnikov National University of Odesa**. It was framed by the partnership between the cities of Gdańsk and Odesa. But the non eligibility of Ukrainian partners to the Alliance's funds has blocked the decision. In other cases, Ukrainian partners are associated partners. **E³UDRES²** has invited **Bohdan Khmelnytskyi National University of Cherkasy, Cherkasy State Business College, Sumy State University** as associate partners with the intention to base a future strategy of cooperation on practical experience, from engaging 60 Ukrainian staff in more than 30 events since autumn 2023, two project proposals on digitalisation involving 34 academics in the E³UDRES²Bank of researchers in order to enhance the academic and research co-operation. Reflecting the regional-focused mission of E³UDRES², strengthened partnership between regions of Valmiera in Latvia and Cherkassy in Ukraine showed the first example to build upon. Since 2023, **NEOLAiA** leadership has had regular meetings with its 4 Ukrainian associated partners in view of inviting them to the Alliance's thematic networks, based on calls funded at the national level in Sweden; in addition, the Alliance reacted swiftly to the shocking bombing of one of its partners **Sumy State University** on Palm Sunday in April 2025 by sending furniture (e.g., computers) and spreading the information at universities on how to donate.
- Example 6: MTU (Munster Technological University, Ireland) is a partner in the **INGENIUM** Alliance. To show solidarity with the 100,000 Ukrainians living in Ireland, MTU worked with local community support and integration agencies to provide online workshops for applicants to Irish universities (advice on the application process, academic programmes and related career issues, 7/7 online assistance). MTU has hosted the NMT (Ukrainian University Entrance Examination) in 2024 and in 2025 for all of the university applicants living in Ireland and Northern Ireland (560+ students in 2025).

Based on several Alliances' feedback, we can list but a few of the **challenges** met:

- **Sustainability** issue of support and network to secure the academic assets of Ukraine and enable students to study in Ukraine;
- **Community sensitivity** in the EU is decreasing after 3 years of war which erodes motivation, activism and perseverance in helping in Ukraine and assisting refugees in the various EU countries;
- **Competing priorities** within the Alliances, starting with the length it takes to set up internally the alliance that can slowdown the inclusion of additional activities born out of the necessity of the war;
- **Ukrainian HEIs belonging to an Alliance have not benefitted from the Alliances' subsidies so far:** to compensate, alternative funding schemes have been sought, which has generated administrative hurdles from a legal, time and operational perspective.

BEST PRACTICES BASED ON NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN INITIATIVES

Alliances have been quick in proposing actions. This has been mainly done via the **preparation of applications for calls for a project under national and European funding schemes, to compensate the impossibility to use funding for Ukrainian partners via the Alliances**. Compared to single HEIs, Alliances can give access to a European network with cross-border opportunities and a series of innovative strategies, translated into harmonised processes and tools that are getting operationalised. They can also provide support by contributing with expertise from different countries to initiatives set by one of the partners of the Alliance.

Securing local, national or European funding to assist Ukrainian colleagues and institutions has therefore been key in giving a capacity of HEIs and Alliances to deliver activities and have some impact, and some results are presented below. Ukrainian partners have shown an incredible dedication to join, learn and contribute, despite all other issues to solve. Actions have been delivered generating more learning and knowledge opportunities, be it for students, academics and staff or governance level, aiming at a **balanced win-win cooperation**.

However, such additional tasks have not been without challenges for the teams and for the strategic level of action of HEIs and Alliances. To name but a few of these challenges: time-consuming call applications, intensity of the deadlines, time needed for the preparation and evaluation of the activities performed, in an already extremely intensive implementation phase of Alliances, and the overall coherence with the Alliance's strategies as well as the issue of the sustainability of activities.

National initiatives:

In addition to the NAWA initiative in **Poland**, national support schemes for HEIs and Alliances in cooperation with Ukraine have been set across Europe, e.g.:

- **Sweden** ([here link](#), e.g., as a result the alliance **HEROES** with the **University of Halmstad** collaborates in the areas of cybersecurity and agriculture including student and teacher mobility, development of joint courses and other student activities, collaboration with Ukrainian enterprises).
- **Germany** ([here](#), additional [link](#)): **European university at Viadrina** (Francfort/Oder) has won a DAAD grant of 2,5 million euro (2024-2028) to support the Interdisciplinary Ukrainian studies competence network, with other German universities such as **Humboldt University** and **Freie Universität in Berlin**, with a possible scaling-up at the **ERUA's** alliance level. Another example of DAAD support went to **UAS Fulda** allowing German partners to enhance participation of Ukrainian staff and students at **E³UDRES²** alliance meetings and workshops on European values and civic engagement.
- **Austria** ([link](#)): **Aurora's International Peace conference** organised at the University of Innsbrück in February 2025 brought 300 participants to discuss the role of higher education in peace-building, with the support of local, national and European sponsors.
- **Slovakia**: Scholarships for excellent researchers threatened by the war in Ukraine have been proposed by the Ministry of Education, Research, Development and Youth (**ULYSSEUS**)
- **France**: Institut français in Kyiv is supporting via e.g., programme Nadiya offering scholarships for researchers in science engineering, MSCA (e.g., co-funding LightinParis at **Paris Saclay University**) and in cultural diplomacy (event "Le voyage en Ukraine", scheduled in December 2025).

European funding schemes: rationale, results and challenges

As previously underlined (based on EUA, 2025), Erasmus+ is considered as a positive instrument by a third of the survey respondents to provide mobility opportunities and ease cooperation with Ukrainian partners. The EC brochure "[Building hope: Europe's solidarity with Ukraine](#)" showcases 15 projects providing support to individuals. It is seen as a relevant tool to implement reforms in higher education, too, e.g., capacity building, digital support, green transition, mobility, intercultural communication and languages. Below are there a series of examples based on Alliances.

However, the structure of the calls according to 3 actions (mobility, capacity-building and partnership) limits the scope of innovation that is at the heart of Alliances' strategies, and may lead to repetitive activities. In addition, applying to calls is time-consuming for the project teams and has only a limited field or sector and time length, therefore it cannot provide the basis for a strategic long-term institutional collaboration.

Examples of European funds used by Alliances to support actions in Ukraine (non exhaustive list):

- **4EU+** has launched the **Eastern Partnership University Cluster** in October 2022, based on the Eastern partnership programme: it brings together 12 universities from the EU and Eastern partnership countries, which aims to systematically develop inter-university cooperation in education, science and research ([link](#))
- **EC2U**, in addition to the use of mobility grants under KA1, under the coordination of the **University of Poitiers**, associated the **Ivan Franko National University of Lviv** to the KA2 Cooperation partnership project EUNIVERSE on improving the institutional environment for incoming and outgoing mobility, based on European values; it is a follow up of the UNISAFE project led by the **University of Pavia**
- **EPICUR** is part of a satellite project under the Erasmus+ special window opened in 2023 for the creation of an Open digital education environment for Ukrainian universities, coordinated by **Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv**, with the contributions of the **University of Strasbourg** and the **University Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań**
- **EUPeace** and **FILMEU** have partnered to apply to a Creative Europe call early 2025
- "**UNIVERSEH 2.0 extended for Ukraine**" is an Erasmus+ cooperation partnership project between UNIVERSEH alliance and **Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University** (Ukraine) as an associated partner to allow for the participation of students and lecturers to conferences, among other things. A tangible result is the launch of the e-course for "University analog astronauts space trainings", tailored to preparing potential participants to space missions ([link](#)). Another example is the multidisciplinary Jean Monnet module "Radiation safety: physical aspect" that emerged from a SWOT analysis on course content revision ([link](#))
- In the case of **CIVICA**, Erasmus+ grants have served compensating the non renewal of the NAWA scheme in 2025 in order to invite 15 scholars as speakers in conferences such as CIVICA's Global forum at **IE University** (Spain), trainers or experts in activities organised by the alliance (and not in a separate portfolio of activities), from 5 universities in Ukraine (**Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman** (KNEU); **Donetsk National University named after Vasyl Stus** (DonNU); **Ukrainian Catholic University** (UCU); **National University of Kyiv Mohyla Academy** (NaUKMA); **Kyiv School of Economics** (KSE).

Last but not least, in the frame of institutional networks such as **European University Association** and the **Bologna group**, emergency support has been launched to share key information and processes on automatic recognition between the EU and Ukraine (example: [AR25 project](#)) and more generally prepare for EU accession (alignement of standards).

Thanks to their capacity to establish well defined action plan, based on a selection of themes, planned on the long run, **Alliances are able to answer the needs formulated by their Ukrainian partners and are well positioned university networks to achieve some impact on the HE and research ecosystem in Ukraine and in Europe, according to the priorities set by the Ukrainian and European policy-makers:** in particular, they are in the capacity to

- **rise the student and academic exchanges with Ukraine** via an increased number of Alliances' applications to Erasmus+ calls to ease mobility via inter-institutional agreements, secure continuity of Ukrainian academia, provide salaries via scholarships
- **Work on joint innovative academic activities** with one or more Ukrainian partners in order to achieve more integration and impact: (e.g., **T4EU** with **University of Alicante** and **Mariupol State University, EURECA-PRO**). Alliances are working to embed their cooperation with Ukraine into their institutions (e.g., visiting professor or any mobility is not "ad hoc", instead it is for credits so that it counts for the completion of the academic year and to get the diploma)
- **(re) or (up)skilling initial and life-long learners** (see World Bank 2024 labour market survey [here](#)) in Ukraine and for refugees in Europe, in the prospect of their return to Ukraine, e.g.,
 - **STARS EU:** entrepreneurship hubs at Ukrainian universities
 - **EPICUR** via the DiGiUni project for an Open digital environment for Ukrainian universities
 - Partner universities crossing alliances: e.g., **European university at Viadrina** with **Adam Mickiewicz University** in Poznań ran the first German-Polish-Ukrainian summerschool "start-ups, transfer and digital studies" attended by 30 students. A second session was organised in Toruń "Common Europe as space and challenge" in September 2024 ([link](#)).
- **Develop research:** Ukrainian studies, demining, natural resources, nuclear power, engineering, health, rehabilitation & psychology, preparedness to different crises, economy, ecological recovery... Some examples from the field of **Ukrainian studies**:
 - **ERUA: European University at Viadrina** has been developing its capacity in this field by establishing the [Viadrina Center of Polish and Ukrainian studies](#) in May 2023, through a merger of the Centre of Interdisciplinary Polish studies and the Entangled History of Ukraine chair. Goal is to develop an expertise about both countries historically and in the present day, taking into account their European and global connections and the transnational perspective
 - **BAUHAUS4EU** and the [Global coalition of Ukrainian studies](#)
 - **4EU+** and **EUniWell** organised a [conference](#) at **Warsaw University** on the development of Ukrainian studies in Europe in May 2025
- **Build resilience and prepare for peace:** resilience and preparedness to crises; reinstall dialogue, critical analysis, knowledge acquisition and development at the heart of the learners' study pathways and in the Ukrainian society after martial law (as part of other initiatives such as [here](#) – National platform of resilience and social cohesion):
 - **Aurora's conference** on "the role of higher education in peace-building" in February 2025, organised by the **University of Innsbruck** (Austria) in cooperation with **Karazin University, Palacky University in Olomouc** (Czech Republic) and the **Free University of Amsterdam**
 - **EUPeace overall Alliance's strategy**
 - **SEA-EU** summer school "for the promotion of democratic values", symbolically located in Gdańsk where the Solidarity movement started in the late 1970s, [link](#).
 - **CIVICA** "KIND conference" at **European University Institute in Florence** (Italy) and **SRIDE** project on informal diplomacy and the role of resilience in the academic community, [link](#).
- Supporting **Eastern regions, in particular Ukraine and its neighbouring countries:** for instance,
 - **T4EU** worked on a "roadmap of support for remote universities" (E+ BOOST project)
 - **4EU+** has launched the Eastern Partnership University Cluster
 - **CIVICA** within CIVICA4Ukraine issued good practices of CIVICA universities as an outcome of the research visits, and **SGH** organised a study visit to Brussels

- **E³UDRES²** via **Vidzeme UAS** supported bilateral cooperation between Valmiera region (Latvia) with the partnering authorities in the Cherkassy region, the model which will be further explored in order to strengthen the regional focus of the Alliance.
- **University reform and governance:**
 - Following the discussion on the future of Ukrainian universities at the **University Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań**, attended by more than 60 rectors and pro-rectors of Ukrainian universities in October 2024, Supervisory Boards were established in 5 Ukrainian universities
 - **4EU+** organised 2 editions of the Student conference including representatives from student governments from various universities. The involvement of Ukrainian student representatives opened the door to future cooperation that could support the development of a student governance model in Ukraine, inspired by European standards.
- One of the outcomes of the CIVICA-Ukraine High Level at SGH in March 2023 was the creation of the **Alliance of Ukrainian universities** under the leadership of the CIVICA4Ukraine partners (Kyiv School of Economics and Ukrainian Catholic University).

HEIs in Europe and Alliances are not alone mobilising in solidarity with Ukraine in Europe and in the world: other regional academic funding schemes have been launched, e.g., in the UK ([updates here](#) under the 100 year partnership agreement with science and technology as key pillars, signed in January 2025; twinning initiative set in 2022 whereby 7 Ukrainian HEIs have been twinned with counterparts in the UK, US, Canadian and Belgium, [link](#)).

TOWARDS STRATEGIC PLANNING

With a couple of exceptions, cooperation with Ukraine was not part of the priorities set by Alliances from the outset. Cooperation has developed mainly because of the full-scale war and first of all in the name of **solidarity**, to assist with immediate needs, welcome students and staff, support the (re)building of capacities of HEIs in Ukraine, stay close to each other and make it known via joint statements. It is worth underlining that the most recent Alliances are also many more with one or more Ukrainian partners from the beginning: out of 14 selected alliances in 2024, they are 9 with one or more Ukrainian partners. The various facets of the cooperation with Ukraine have produced intense, direct, human encounters, between EU partners that have learned from different national realities and with partners from Ukraine. It echoes the shared concerns of the academic world because of geopolitical crises, such as security, freedom, in particular freedom of science. We have learned a lot from each other, in particular about **resilience**, and this is meant to last and even develop further more.

Because of **strategic planning** being at the core of their actions, anchored in their integrated governance processes, Alliances regularly reflect about their updated shared interests and can decide to adapt their action plan in an efficient and sustainable way. Based on several years of experimenting and on the mutual learning across Alliances, they have focused more and more of their activities around the support to the academic community in Ukraine to assist in immediate and more long-term needs. They are now ready to set long-term partnerships with one or more Ukrainian universities, going beyond the time and project frame, which is an important dimension of building international relations.

Given the extraordinary circumstances of the full-scale war in Ukraine, we are asking for a **framework for a sustainable cooperation between European universities alliances (not exclusively, other networks of HEIs can join) and Ukrainian HEIs to be initiated at the EU level, possibly synchronised with national funding schemes**. The EU can greatly benefit from the efficiency of our already existing networking (and next steps) and show political support towards a more integrated European higher education cooperation with Ukraine. For Alliances, it will allow them to structure their bottom-up activities in a strategic way and in the long run, according to a common frame of action. Activities will be defined according to the regular needs analyses that will be done within each Alliance, based on the feedback provided by Ukrainian colleagues and institutions. The FOREU4ALL topical group "Cooperation with Ukraine" will serve to review the policy priorities in Ukraine and in the EU, and to share the needs identified in order to respond to them in the most appropriate and efficient way, avoiding for instance duplication or repetition.

So far, some Alliances have planned strategically their solidarity action with Ukraine by establishing ad hoc contact points. For instance, **ENHANCE** has created a "Taskforce for Ukraine", **UNITA** has established a project office at **Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University**, and **EUT+** Global Outreach Office is coordinating the internationalisation activities of partners with a special emphasis on Ukraine. **Aurora** has had a CDS Team at **Karazin University in Kharkiv** from 2019, and an action plan. It is important to underline that the members of the newly created FOREU4ALL topical group "Cooperation with Ukraine" are in their vast majority made of representatives of the university, either (vice)-rectors, (vice)-deans and cabinet members or advisors.

Alternatively, based on NAWA experience and in particular the connections created by the numerous activities such as in the case of the **University Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań (EPICUR)**, the efforts have focused on structuring long-term networks of a group of alliances and a group of Ukrainian universities, that are members or not of an alliance. Slightly different, **FORTHEM** alliance has consistently pursued a well-defined goal in its collaboration with Ukrainian HEIs: to reinforce existing partnerships and establish a strong, inclusive academic network that brings Ukrainian universities closer to the European (Higher) Education and Research Area. A comprehensive mapping exercise was conducted and identified 29 Ukrainian HEIs already linked by formal agreements with at least one FORTHEM university. The strategy centers on enriching these partnerships through joint research initiatives, academic mobilities, and the exchange of knowledge and expertise. FORTHEM serves as a hub for linking bilateral efforts and thematic partnerships into a broader, multi-institutional framework. A central objective is to prepare the groundwork for selected Ukrainian HEIs to join the FORTHEM Alliance as associated partners in the future.

How to do it?

Proposals currently discussed among Alliances for strategic planning: structure long-term networks, use alliances as bridges and as learning platforms to know more about each other:

- Continue and increase the **personal connections** between Ukrainian HEIs and European universities Alliances (administrative staff; academic; leadership), **fostering grassroots initiatives**. The main tool available for now is Erasmus+ KA1 mobility grants, of which a substantial quota shall be dedicated to these connections; also develop virtual learning (e.g., COIL) to promote internationalisation without extra-funding for travel and accommodation;
- In order to make these exchanges and follow up decisions as strategic as possible, favour the **participation of Ukrainian HEIs leadership to governance meetings as observers** to improve their awareness of ongoing developments within the Alliance in a timely manner, and prepare for full or associated membership; appoint "**Ukraine Liaison officers**" in each Alliance to strengthen the coherence in topics and timeline of the various activities, going beyond the projects' temporary frame, and to foster the cooperation within Alliances as well as easing the communication between HEIs in Ukraine;
- Continue and increase the **exchange of best practices and assistance to relaunch the higher education sector in the post-war context in Ukraine**: support connections and develop a structured learning from the exchanges between students, administrative and academic staff, leadership in relation to e.g., the attraction and retention of students, internationalisation, life-long learning, etc; assist in infrastructure needs because of the destructions of the war, for instance with decommissioned but functioning equipment from HEIs in the EU;
- Undergo a **mapping of the activities of Ukrainian HEIs in order to identify, based on well-grounded analyses, the concrete areas and tools or solutions they can contribute and benefit from, in ongoing Alliances' activities** and / or learn from with potential future collaborations (in EU funded projects the participation of institutions from all candidate countries to the EU, especially Ukraine, would be welcomed);
- **Based on their respective fields of excellence in education and research**, Alliances can contribute to cooperation projects funded under the **Ukraine facility investment schemes and future assistance schemes funded by the EU and its Member states**;
- **Political priority of EU accession: develop Ukrainian studies in relation to European studies in order to learn more about Ukraine and the EU in the preparation process for EU accession on both parts**. The past experience of Jean Monnet activities and their role in preparing for accession can serve as a good practice in developing teaching and research on Ukrainian and EU studies; Alliances can widen the impact by proposing to the student and staff communities of their universities, as well as a broader audience of citizens, **to get to know each other better and develop a narrative about Ukrainian accession to the EU that is well-informed, avoiding the damaging fake news**.

We welcome the European Commission's MFF proposal 2028-2034 to dedicate 100 bn euro to the reconstruction of Ukraine and to support the Eastern regions, and we advocate for education and research being fully part of the solution in the resilience and the reconstruction initiatives for Ukraine; we welcome the enhanced support to Ukraine's integration into the European Education Area in the proposed Erasmus+ regulation 2028-34;

We call for more national support in the Member States comprising an Alliance's dimension and for national and European funding to become more synchronised;

We are supportive of the European parliament's draft report on a "New vision for the European universities alliances" that "welcomes value-based initiatives such as the cooperation in solidarity with Ukraine and the role of alliances in preparing for accession with Eastern neighbourhood countries";

Reconstruction of Ukraine needs coordination: we support EUA recommendation (2023) on inter-institutional collaboration as a key success factor for (long-term) continued support for Ukrainian higher education, and this report shows that Alliances can be attractive and efficient instruments;

We support EUA recommendation (2025) on improving crisis resilience and response in the frame of Erasmus+ (recommendation 11), with an ambitious programme to "support scholars at risk and support at-risk students", in line with the "Choose Europe for science" initiative;

For the Erasmus+ work programme 2026-2027, we call for

- setting the cooperation with Ukraine among the possible criteria for Alliances' goals;
- opening calls e.g., to support the appointment of Ukraine liaison officers within Alliances and the management of existing strategic partnerships in order to integrating Ukrainian HEIs into European innovative practices by and for networks of EU HEIs, in line with the policy priorities and expected outcomes in education and research of Ukraine and the EU;
- in Horizon Europe, increase access to funding for joint research projects with Ukrainian partners (individuals, institutions);
- in HE and research, allow for the creation of structural inclusion mechanisms.

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JOINT STATEMENT

Open Letter addressed to Executive Vice-President Roxana Mînzatu

7 May 2025

United in solidarity with higher education and research in Ukraine

We are European universities alliances spread out across the diversity of 35 countries of the continent, connecting and uniting universities from the European Union (EU) and beyond up to Ukraine. We all believe in excellence, openness, and collaboration to drive ambitious programmes for seamless education and research and build a resilient and competitive Europe.

Since the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by the Russian federation in February 2022, we have been standing in solidarity with Ukraine, as the vast majority of the higher education sector in Europe has done. For the last three years, we have directly assisted thousands of students, academic colleagues and friends, and more than 100 higher education institutions in coping with physical destruction, lack of equipment and human resources turnover and burnout due to martial law consequences.

Beyond assistance in the war context, cooperation has been enhanced between European and Ukrainian universities. Since 2021, Ukrainian higher education has been involved in nearly 2.000 Erasmus projects in total. Ukrainian universities have taken the lead as coordinators in 15 capacity building projects. We are aware that many more reforms are needed and therefore more capacity-building efforts required, and we will continue participating in that.

In addition, cooperation has taken place in the frame and according to the innovative objectives of our alliances. Today, 35 alliances out of 65 have one or more Ukrainian universities either as full or associated partners, or are actively cooperating in areas that are central to their activities. To name but a few, these refer to peer learning or development in digital education, interdisciplinary joint programmes, the governance of university networks, the setting up of flexible learning pathways. Balanced win-win cooperation is the way we work.

This Open letter, and our previous joint statements released in 2022 and 2024 with follow up dissemination events, illustrate the inter-alliances efforts to share, and the capacity to learn from our respective best practices with Ukraine. It also aims at reaching out to the universities in Ukraine not yet in the loop. We as alliances state our continued solidarity with Ukraine, in an unstable and preoccupying international geopolitical context. In this perspective,

- We call for the EU and its Member states to play an active role in supporting the current Ukrainian needs in the higher education sector and more particularly for the displaced universities. We advocate for education and research being fully part of the solution in the resilience and the reconstruction initiatives for Ukraine, as it is stated in the Ukraine facility plan.
- Based on our fields of excellence in education and research, we can contribute to cooperation projects funded under the Ukraine facility investment schemes and are happy to connect our national contact points and work with them. We are willing to assist our counterparts and the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine in covering current needs in re-skilling, up-skilling and in research.

JOINT STATEMENT

Open Letter addressed to Executive Vice-President Roxana Mînzatu
7 May 2025

- We call for the specific neighbourhood programmes and the financing in the context of the accession negotiations of Ukraine to the EU to offer opportunities for calls to which alliances could apply. It would help us structure our action and make a more concrete commitment in view of the preparation for accession.
- We call for the European Commission, on an exceptional flexibility basis, to allow using the alliances' funding under Erasmus+ for performing activities with involvement of the Ukrainian partners and for events in Ukraine where the added value to our projects objectives is justified. In fact, some Ukrainian partners have already best practices to share which can be beneficial to our deliverables.

After several years of cooperation, we are ready to play an active role in assisting in a crisis, learning from each other and growing for a common European future. We know what can be done and that we can do it, and we need support in achieving it.

The Open letter is supported by the following 35 alliances:

REFERENCES & ABBREVIATIONS

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CULT committee report "A new vision for the European universities alliances" (adopted in CULT committee, final vote in plenary to be expected in September 2025, European parliament)
Follow up event report Strasbourg "European and Ukrainian universities cooperation: state of play and future perspectives" (2024)

Scholars at risk:

Inspireurope Policy recommendations "Expanding opportunities in Europe for researchers at risk" 2022
Initiatives for Ukraine, European University Institute network (19 May 2025)

EU accession and the role of HE:

Permacchange via enlargement, EPC report (2025)
UDICE position paper on the role of research and HE in the Global Gateway strategy (released March 2025)

ABBREVIATIONS

BIP - Blended Intensive Programme

CULT committee - Culture and Education committee at the European parliament

EEA - European Education Area

EU - European Union

EUA - European University Association

FOREU4ALL - Community of practice of the current 65 European Universities Alliances, funded under Erasmus+ (2024-2028)

HE - Higher education

HEIs - Higher education institutions

MFF - Multi-annual Financial Framework

13.04.2025

СУСПІЛЬНЕ СУМИ

КОНГРЕС-ЦЕНТР СУМДУ